

Influence Gamification Design to E-Commerce Business Objectives

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The ever evolving field of video game software development, especially in the context of gamification projects, presents a wide range of challenges and opportunities. This extensive research brings together insights from various studies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the hurdles faced in game development. It also introduces an innovative framework for gamification project requirements and explores the impact of gamification on consumer behavior within the Indonesian e commerce industry.

The initial part of the research dives into the complexities involved in game development, identifying four main categories of challenges through literature review and post-mortem analysis; game development itself, internal issues within teams, technical aspects and effective time management. By analyzing 69 sections detailing "what went wrong" from six project postmortem reports, this study highlights common deficiencies in documentation, team management problems and technological obstacles. These findings emphasize the importance of adopting a structured approach when navigating the intricacies of game development, particularly when implementing gamification initiatives. To address the existing gaps in tools for gamification project requirements, the second phase of this research introduces a novel software model that combines principles from Ahlmann and Gastl's artifact paradigm with methodologies such as the Gamification Model Canvas Evolution and Lean Gamification Canvas. Developed through literature review and subject matter expert interview, this model offers a practical framework for businesses to effectively implement gamification strategies. It ensures alignment with business objectives while also considering technical feasibility. However, further examination and feedback are needed to validate its effectiveness across different types of gamification projects within a single organization. The last part of the study focuses on the growing e commerce industry in Indonesia and explores how gamification design impacts business goals. By surveying fifty Indonesian mobile app users, these participants were selected through random sampling. We collected data on demographics and user perceptions using questionnaires, which were then analyzed using PLS SEM. The research reveals

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that gamification design positively influences user engagement and purchasing behavior. However, it has limited impact on advocacy and significant behavioral changes, which is surprising given that increased engagement doesn't necessarily lead to higher purchasing rates. This suggests that other factors come into play. It's interesting to note that being fully immersed in an activity, often called being in a "flow" state, has a greater impact on users likelihood to recommend something compared to gamification design alone.

To sum up, this research offers valuable insights into the challenges of game development and introduces a new framework for gamification project requirements. It also sheds light on the nuanced effects of gamification design in the e-commerce industry. The study emphasizes the importance of taking a balanced approach to gamification by recognizing its benefits in enhancing user engagement while also acknowledging its limitations. Further research is encouraged to refine the proposed model and investigate factors that influence the outcomes of gamification strategies in developer side.

Keywords: challenge, design, development, e-commerce, gamification, software

Authors Biography

Junaldi Dwijaputra currently holds the position of Head of Business Gamification, at Agate. Focusing in gamification and product management area with over six years of experience in industries such as mining, technology. Junaldi completed his Master of Business Administration degree at the School of Business and Management Institut Teknologi Bandung. His research focus during his studies was on Gamification resulting in the publication of gamification research and presentations at conferences. Currently he also take Doctoral Program at School of Interdisciplinary Management and Technology, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember, Surabaya, Indonesia

Prof. Dr. Diana Purwitasari, S.Kom. M.Sc. is an academic and researcher, in the field of Informatics Engineering specializing in Natural Language Processing (NLP). She has achieved a Doctorate in Electrical Engineering from the Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (ITS) demonstrating her dedication to advancing technology and engineering education. Throughout her career Prof. Purwitasari has held important roles. Currently in 2021 she serves as the Vice Dean of the Faculty of Electrical Technology and Intelligent Informatics.

Ellya Zulaikha, ST., M.Sn., Ph.D., who holds a Bachelors degree (ST.) and a Master of Science, in Design (M.Sn.) has been teaching at the Department of Industrial Product Design at ITS Surabaya since 1998. She completed her studies in Product Design at ITS in 1993. Obtained her Masters degree from Institut Teknologi Bandung in 2003. In 2014 she successfully defended her Ph.D. Thesis on Collaborative Design at Queensland University of Technology in Australia. Previously serving as the department head for Industrial Product Design she now holds the position of Vice Dean within the Faculty of Architecture, Design and Planning, at ITS. Ellya Zulaikha is also a member of ADPII (Indonesian Alliance of Industrial Product Designers).